

The results indicate that chemical properties of rice grain, particularly Mg content, and Mg/K were higher in favorable soil types than in unfavorable ones where the plants grow more slowly. Some characters related to cooking quality, however, could be reversed because the starch tissue of grain produced under an inferior soil class may be caused by slow translocation and by insufficient nutrient uptake of plants. ■

Yield potential

An assessment for yield estimation in upland rainfed ecosystem of Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh

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The relation between grain yield and yield components can be expressed as Grain yield (g m^{-2}) = No. panicles m^{-2} \times no. spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ \times % fertile spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ \times weight of single spikelet (g) (De Datta 1981, Arraudeau and Vergara 1988). This formula does not hold well for rainfed upland rice when the paired t test is applied. Therefore I attempted various multiplication factors and finally ended up with 0.5, as described in this note. A complete block design with three replications was used during the wet seasons (WS) of 1992 and 1993, with 26 and 21 entries, respectively. They were direct-seeded (10 g m^{-2} in eight plots, 4 m in length, with 25-cm row spacing. The soil was low in available N and P_2O_5 and medium in available K_2O (220.0, 9.6, and 220.0 kg ha^{-1}) at pH 5.6. A dose of 40-8.8-8.3 kg NPK ha^{-1} was applied. Five plants were randomly selected from each plot to record observations on a randomly selected 1-m^2 area (Tables 1 and 2). Grain yield was estimated by substituting the yield attributes in the conventional and a modified formula for all the genotypes. Paired t tests for observed grain yield

Table 1. Yield attributes and estimated grain yield of extra early and early rice genotypes under upland rainfed ecosystem. Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India. 1992 WS.

Genotype	Panicles m^{-2} (no.)	Filled spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g m^{-2})	Estimated grain yield (g m^{-2})	
						Conventional	Modified
R281 PP31-1	295	53.5	80.7	24.0	126.3	305.5	152.7
R302-111	262	58.5	73.3	24.0	132.0	269.5	134.8
JR80-4-6	342	40.9	81.4	19.4	100.7	221.0	110.5
JR82-10	322	46.5	73.0	23.3	122.0	254.6	127.3
JR84-7-1-19	270	51.2	77.8	28.1	187.7	302.1	151.0
RWR78-71-9	387	41.7	79.0	82.8	142.0	290.5	145.2
RNR-1446	341	40.7	89.9	22.7	158.3	283.6	141.8
CR92-65	260	52.9	83.6	26.3	152.0	302.7	151.0
Vanprabha	217	45.1	77.2	25.0	107.2	189.1	94.5
Heera	281	46.3	69.8	22.4	140.8	203.5	101.7
Poorva	339	46.7	76.3	26.8	129.6	323.5	161.8
Kalinga 3	362	44.5	81.7	23.8	167.3	312.9	156.5
Tulasi	348	52.1	82.0	24.8	152.5	368.5	184.2
Annada	340	57.5	81.3	26.9	177.6	427.4	213.7
Jawahar 75	322	48.4	77.6	22.7	156.0	272.6	136.3
RR180-1	263	48.9	79.4	26.5	166.0	270.7	135.4
RR51-1-1-7	274	41.3	76.0	25.0	162.3	214.9	107.5
RR151-3	301	42.5	86.7	24.7	159.3	274.1	137.0
Aditya	272	40.2	81.4	28.6	176.3	254.5	127.2
Rasi	345	46.0	80.6	22.0	138.3	281.4	140.7
Tellahamsa	339	51.3	82.6	23.7	182.7	340.8	170.4
B3619C-PB8	302	69.5	87.1	23.4	156.7	428.1	214.0
Kakudo	290	48.6	80.4	21.8	158.7	246.9	123.5
Palsul	254	80.7	86.1	19.5	177.6	344.1	172.0
Badoldhan	217	86.8	86.9	26.2	203.7	429.2	214.6
Bhilaimuch	321	79.8	85.3	9.8	115.0	214.2	107.1
Mean	302	52.4	80.6	23.6	151.9	293.3	146.6
CD (0.05)	89.3	10.9	5.2	2.8	-	-	-
t value	-	-	-	-	-	12.9	0.96
Goodness of fit	-	-	-	-	-	***a	ns ^b

^a*** = significant, $p=0.01$. ^bnonsignificant.

Table 2. Yield attributes and estimated grain yield of extra early and early rice genotypes under upland rainfed ecosystem. Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India. 1993 WS.

Genotype	Panicles m^{-2} (no.)	Filled spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g m^{-2})	Estimated grain yield (g m^{-2})	
						Conventional	Modified
R281 PP31-1	275	63.1	83.2	24.1	140.4	347.9	173.9
JR80-4-6	289	66.4	85.8	22.7	204.6	373.6	186.8
JR82-1-10	309	68.4	80.4	27.2	253.4	459.6	229.8
JR84-7-1-19	279	71.1	83.2	27.8	283.4	459.3	229.7
RWR78-71-9	335	64.3	84.0	24.0	257.9	434.6	217.3
RR149-177	274	51.8	85.6	24.3	168.4	295.4	147.7
RR151-3	236	68.1	85.4	27.9	205.9	382.9	191.2
RR166-645	256	74.5	82.9	28.5	230.4	450.9	225.5
RR180-1	213	63.0	87.9	29.4	227.1	347.2	173.6
Kalinga 3	294	60.6	80.7	24.8	165.4	356.1	178.0
Annada	272	76.2	88.9	27.6	285.4	509.3	254.6
Poorva	260	51.0	82.1	27.9	138.4	303.7	151.8
Aditya	306	60.6	88.7	29.6	189.1	487.3	243.6
Tulasi	268	69.9	90.0	25.4	270.4	428.6	214.3
Rasi	305	67.1	87.3	24.1	250.9	430.4	215.2
Tellahamsa	283	67.0	88.2	26.1	255.4	436.9	218.4
RNR1446	298	64.9	89.1	25.2	226.6	434.5	217.3
Badoldhan	199	79.0	90.5	28.2	197.5	401.1	200.5
IR55423-15	191	83.3	86.2	27.9	192.9	382.5	191.2
TRC87-2-51	274	86.9	86.5	21.5	257.1	442.6	221.3
CR692-600	242	81.9	88.5	26.5	232.1	465.2	232.6
Mean	269	68.5	85.9	26.2	218.0	415.0	207.6
CD (0.05)	70	16.2	4.8	2.4	-	-	-
t value	-	-	-	-	-	16.2	1.45
Goodness of fit	-	-	-	-	-	***a	ns ^b

^a***=significant, $p=0.01$. ^bnonsignificant.

were similarly calculated for both the years of study.

The test assumes that both values were at par, and results showed that goodness of fit was significant for the conventional formula and nonsignificant for the modified formula. One of the reasons for the difference might be the prevailing climatic conditions. The low fertility and typically poor yield of the upland ecosystem may be attrib-

table to the low average of sunshine hours per day in the wet season in Bastar Plateau Zone. The average sunshine hours per day during the crop growing months (Jun, Jul, Aug, and Sep) were 6.3, 3.7, 2.2, 6.7 in 1992 and 5.6, 3.9, 2.5, 5.3 in 1993. Cloudy weather prevailed during both vegetative and reproductive crop stages. Hence, use of the modified formulas seems to be accurate for assessing extra-early and

early rice genotypes grown in the upland rainfed ecosystem of Bastar Plateau Zone.

Cited references

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De Datta SK. 1981. Principles and practices of rice production. New York: John Wiley & Sons. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

GPIR-22: a gene pool developed to improve partial resistance to blast of upland rice

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Durability of blast resistance is a major concern in the upland ecosystem. Partial resistance may be more durable than complete resistance because it appears to be largely race-nonspecific. It cannot be assessed, however, unless one has a virulent strain effective against major genes. An isolate compatible with the highest possible number of parents may be used to overcome major genes in a population, which is then purged of the remaining major gene(s) conditioning resistance to such an isolate. Only the major genes efficient against the chosen isolate are discarded and the other major genes retained. Once such a population is built, lines with a susceptible infection type but having a reduced relative infection efficiency after inoculation with the compatible isolate can easily be selected. The effective major genes that were purged from the population can be introduced at the end of the program in order to have the best partial resistance and the best major genes. GPIR-22 is a poly-cytoplasmic gene

pool we constituted following this strategy.

Eight monoconidial isolates among those we used most widely were tested against 50 potential parents using monocyclic inoculation tests in the 1994

dry season (DS). The isolate V85-0256, which has the broadest virulence spectrum and gives consistent results on the parents, was chosen as reference. Based on their isozymic diversity, 24 upland varieties were chosen (see

Building GPIR-22 through circular hybridizations.